

Final report

DFG-Project SCHW 2027/2-1: Hydro-morphodynamic connectivity and ecosystem design in a changing environment

1. General Information

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Project title: Hydro-morphodynamic connectivity and ecosystem design in a changing environment

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2. Summary

2.1. Summary (English)

Connectivity in rivers describes the degree to which matter (e.g., substances, fluids) including organisms, and energy (e.g., heat) are exchanged among spatial units along river ecosystems. It is paramount for the ecological integrity of river ecosystems, but has been severely altered through anthropogenic modifications. The challenges associated with ecosystem degradation and climate change underline the need for advancing in interdisciplinary knowledge,

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investigating and creating optimized and appropriate methods for analysing and balancing connectivity in rivers worldwide. This project's goal was to analyse hydrological and hydro-morphological connectivity patterns and robust design schemes for the adaptation of fluvial ecosystems to attenuate impacts caused by extreme droughts and floods. To this end, this project synthesized hydro-morphological data and literature to establish an open database and advance the understanding of river connectivity. Statistical models were developed to investigate the controls of connectivity properties and to create tools for river landscape optimization. The reviews and meta-analyses accomplished in this project challenge conventional statistical assumptions, in particular under heat and drought as well as changing biogeochemical conditions in the hyporheic zone, which are expected to intensify with climate change. One major accomplishment was one of the first AI-assisted large-scale literature reviews on river connectivity. This review identified 18 key connectivity themes using expert knowledge and Latent Dirichlet Allocation and it revealed major challenges regarding the quantification of hyporheic exchange. In addition, a critical assessment of AI-generated topic summaries showed promising potential but also key deficiencies in accuracy, terminology, and social inclusiveness in the literature on connectivity of aquatic bodies in general.

To support data collection, the MultiPAC system for measuring connectivity along the lateral and vertical dimensions of the hyporheic zone was optimized. Fieldwork surveys during drought conditions at the Rhine River revealed sediment patchiness as a driver of functional connectivity and the decoupling of thermal and hydrological connectivity. A new open-source database for river data, called River Analyst, enabled efficient analysis of riverbed properties using principal component analysis (PCA). For instance, principal components showed that riverbed clogging decreased when fine sediment exceeds 50–55%, offering a data-driven basis for restoration strategies.

Furthermore, enhanced lateral and vertical connectivity patterns were found to be well-established at a recently restored site on the Rhine River. Specifically, removing reinforced banks and levees allowed a sand bank to develop freely, resulting in particularly high lateral and vertical connectivity signatures during drought conditions. This finding suggests that localized bank removal is an efficient design strategy for restoring lateral and vertical connectivity.

In sum, the project outcomes enhance diagnoses for the restoration of river connectivity by using field data, modelling, and machine learning approaches to address eco-morphological challenges.

2.2. Zusammenfassung (Deutsch)

Die Konnektivität in Fließgewässern beschreibt, inwieweit Materie (z.B. Stoffe, Fluide) einschließlich Organismen sowie Energie (z.B. Wärme) zwischen räumlichen Einheiten eines Flussökosystems ausgetauscht werden. Sie ist von zentraler Bedeutung für die ökologische

Integrität, wurde jedoch durch anthropogene Eingriffe erheblich beeinträchtigt. Herausforderungen durch Ökosystemdegradation und Klimawandel machen die Wiederherstellung der Konnektivität fluvialer Ökosystem notwendig. Dies erfordert interdisziplinäre Untersuchungen, um optimierte und angemessene Methoden zur Analyse und Wiederherstellung der Konnektivität. Ziel dieses Projekts war es, hydrologische und hydromorphologische Konnektivitätsmuster sowie robuste Entwurfsansätze zur Wiederherstellung von Flussökosystemkonnektivität zu untersuchen, um die Auswirkungen extremer Dürren und Überschwemmungen abzumildern. Hierzu wurden hydromorphologische Daten und Fachliteratur synthetisiert, eine offene Datenbank erstellt und das Verständnis der Flusskonnektivität vertieft. Statistische Modelle wurden entwickelt, um Steuerungsgrößen der Konnektivität zu identifizieren und Werkzeuge zur Optimierung von Flusslandschaften zu erarbeiten. Die im Projekt durchgeführten Literaturrecherchen und Metaanalysen hinterfragen konventionelle statistische Annahmen, insbesondere unter Hitze- und Dürrebedingungen sowie sich verändernden biogeochemischen Verhältnissen in der hyporheischen Zone, deren Intensivierung infolge des Klimawandels zu erwarten ist. Ein wesentlicher Projekterfolg war eine der ersten KI-gestützten großangelegten Literaturlauswertungen zur Flusskonnektivität, die mithilfe von Expertenwissen und Latent-Dirichlet-Allocation 18 zentrale Themen identifizierte und erhebliche Herausforderungen bei der Quantifizierung des hyporheischen Austauschs aufdeckte. Eine kritische Bewertung von KI-erzeugten Themenzusammenfassungen zeigte zwar vielversprechendes Potenzial, offenbarte jedoch auch wesentliche Defizite hinsichtlich Genauigkeit, Terminologie und sozialer Inklusivität in der Literatur zur Konnektivität aquatischer Systeme.

Für Datenerhebungen wurde das MultiPAC-System zur Messung der vertikalen Konnektivität in der hyporheischen Zone optimiert und auf die laterale Dimension angewendet. Feldmessungen während Dürrebedingungen am Rhein zeigten, dass Sedimentheterogenität ein wesentlicher Faktor funktionaler Konnektivität ist und eine Entkopplung zwischen thermischer und hydrologischer Konnektivität bewirkt. Eine neue quelloffene Flussdatenbank, genannt *River Analyst*, ermöglichte die effiziente Analyse von vertikaler Flussbettkonnektivität mittels Hauptkomponentenanalyse (PCA). Die Hauptkomponenten belegten, dass die Kolmation des Flussbetts abnimmt, wenn der Feinkornanteil 50 – 55 % übersteigt und liefern damit eine datengestützte Grundlage für Renaturierungsstrategien.

Auch wurden an einem erst kürzlich renaturierten Abschnitt des Rheins ausgeprägte laterale und vertikale Konnektivitätsmuster nachgewiesen. Insbesondere der Rückbau von Uferbefestigungen und Deichen ermöglichte die freie Ausbildung einer Sandbank, was während der Trockenperiode zu besonders hohen lateralen und vertikalen Konnektivitätssignaturen führte. Dieses Ergebnis weist darauf hin, dass selektive Uferrückbauten eine effiziente Maßnahme zur Wiederherstellung lateraler und vertikaler Konnektivität sind.

Insgesamt verbessern die Projektergebnisse die Diagnostik der Flusskonnektivität für Renaturierungszwecke, indem Felddaten, Modellierung und maschinelles Lernen kombiniert wurden, um ökomorphologische Herausforderungen zu adressieren.

3. Progress Report

3.1. Background and objectives

River connectivity refers to the degree to which water, sediment, nutrients, heat, and organisms move through and interact within river networks across longitudinal, lateral, vertical, and time dimensions. This connectivity is fundamental to maintaining the ecological integrity and resilience of river ecosystems. However, human interventions such as damming, channelization, and land-use changes have fragmented these systems, leading to degraded ecosystem functions and reduced biodiversity.

In light of increasing climate change pressures, especially the more frequent and intense droughts and floods, understanding, quantifying, and optimizing hydro-morphodynamic connectivity and ecosystem design has become a scientific and operational priority. Yet, quantifying connectivity remains a challenge due to its complex spatial and temporal variability, especially in the hyporheic zone. Specifically, the hyporheic zone refers to the porous substrate region surrounding rivers, where surface water and groundwater exchange. In this zone, structural heterogeneity (e.g., sediment patchiness) governs functional exchange.

This project addressed challenges related to the combined quantification of lateral and vertical connectivity, especially at restoration sites, by conducting a comprehensive review of global river connectivity literature and advancing field-based, analytical, and modeling methods and insights. The overarching aim of this project was to establish robust design schemes for optimizing hydro-morphodynamic connectivity in fluvial ecosystems, with a particular focus on ensuring system resilience under climatic extremes such as droughts and floods. The specific sub-objectives were: (1) the synthesis of existing methods and data for ecosystem enhancement, (2) the parametric, morphodynamic optimization of fluvial landscapes, and (3) the development of design schemes and algorithms for hydro-morphodynamic optimization and hydrological connectivity of aquatic habitats. The outcomes of these objectives, which are described in the next sections, support a new paradigm in river science where connectivity is not merely preserved, but actively engineered through precise, data-informed interventions tailored to evolving environmental challenges.

3.2. Review of literature and data on river connectivity

In alignment with the project goal of synthesizing hydro-morphological parameters describing connectivity (sub-objective 1), a meta-analysis of data available in the literature on a key hydro-morphological connectivity parameters along the longitudinal dimension was conducted,

notably sediment transport (see Schwindt et al., 2023a). This study successfully revealed the significant role of seasonal and climatic variability, challenging traditional models that assume static, averaged conditions. By reviewing and extending a large sediment transport database with remote sensing data, it was demonstrated that conventional Gaussian distribution assumptions inadequately represent natural sediment transport, which is instead better described by extreme value distributions. A key finding was that seasonality and the source of the water in a river, such as snowmelt, glacier melt, or rainfall, statistically influenced the amount of sediment transported more than the presence of dams. This meta-analysis thus notably advanced the precision and applicability of sediment transport estimation within dynamically changing eco-morphological systems.

In addition, an AI-assisted literature review on river connectivity worldwide was conducted (Negreiros et al., under review). In this review, fundamental concepts of river connectivity were examined, alongside associated dimensions and synthesized research on subjects deserving of special attention due to challenges and diverging research, such as the problem of quantifying and balancing connectivity. Using natural language processing tools, notably Latent Dirichlet Allocation, prevalent topics in connectivity research from more than 2,735 publications were identified and collected online. 18 topics in river connectivity literature were tagged, touching on ecological assessments, sediment transport, and hyporheic exchange. Moreover, large language models (LLM) such as GPT-4 hold the promise of augmenting literature reviews due to their powerful processing capabilities. However, vetting such tools is crucial before they can be implemented in any research pipeline, which is why AI-generated topic summaries produced by GPT-4 were evaluated in terms of rigorous scientific standards, such as accuracy of terminology. The results show that GPT-4 performs well in summarizing topics, but involves high epistemic risk, lack of terminology accuracy, and incapability to include socially-inclusive recent research trends. These shortcomings indicate that reviews produced by GPT-4 are still not at par with syntheses generated human experts, and future research should direct efforts toward ethnical equity and fine tuning of LLMs for producing high-quality literature reviews in river research.

3.3. Optimization of experimental and post-processing methods

Previous to the begin of the project, the University of Stuttgart conducted cutting-edge research on novel methods for eco-morphological assessments of riverbed substrates (Seitz, 2020). These methods included frozen sediment samples, the subsequent creation of digital twins for porosity determination, and a novel method for obtaining depth-explicit porewater dissolved oxygen content (concentration and saturation), temperature, and hydraulic conductivity within the hyporheic zone. Aligned with the objectives of the project of collecting hydro-morphological data in the Rhine river, these efforts were continued in this project and a proof-

of-concept for a multi-parameter approach to quantify clogging and vertical hyporheic connectivity was developed (MultiPAC, see Negreiros et al., 2023). Notably, MultiPAC was re-iterated to obtain insights into connectivity in the hyporheic zone of rivers. In addition, aiming at more efficient data collection workflows, the study features optimized routines for post-processing riverbed parameters. This work was fundamental for fulfilling multiple project goals, including fieldwork at the Rhine, and designing optimal measurement programs suitable to assess not only vertical but also lateral connectivity (see section 3.4).

3.4. Spatial signatures of connectivity in the Rhine

With the optimized MultiPAC measurement scheme, two field data collections were accomplished at the Rhine. The measurements were performed when the Rhine was under hydro-meteorological stress during the summer drought of 2022. Two restored sites in the proximity of natural reserves were selected, downstream of the last barrier (Iffezheim Dam). At each site, lateral transects consisting of four MultiPAC points each were investigated, as shown in Figure 1, alongside measurements of hydraulic quantities (3d flow velocity and water depth) and drone imagery.

In alignment with sub-objective 1, spatial signatures of hyporheic connectivity (Negreiros et al., submitted) were investigated in the vertical and lateral dimensions. Notably, multiple parameters characterizing the exchange of surface and subsurface water in the hyporheic zone were quantified. To this end, frozen sediment samples were collected (Figure 1d) and vertical profiles of dissolved oxygen, water temperature, and a hydraulic conductivity proxy (i.e., slurping rates) were measured in the hyporheic zone. Porewater temperature profiles showed little variation over depth despite steep decreases and subsequent re-increases in the dissolved oxygen in the hyporheic zone (Figure 1e-g). These results suggest that hydrological connectivity should be disentangled from thermal connectivity in the Rhine. In addition, a sandy bed interspersed with silt-clay layers (Figure 1d) indicated constrained ad-locum vertical exchange reflected in large differences between surface water and hyporheic water regarding dissolved oxygen, which highlights the role of sediment patchiness as a signature of structural connectivity and driver of functional connectivity.

3.5. River Analyst database

In alignment with sub-objective 1 of synthesizing data on fluvial ecosystems, an open-source database for spatially explicit hydraulic-morphodynamic data was developed (River Analyst, see Negreiros et al., 2024). The database was coded in Django, a Python framework for web development. The establishment of the database framework provided the basis for fulfilling sub-objective 2. By streamlining data handling and analysis processes, the River Analyst database enhances transparency, accessibility, and scalability in hydro-environmental research. River Analyst also has the capability to perform Principal Component Analysis (PCA)

on sediment and hydraulic characteristics related to hyporheic exchange, particularly addressing riverbed clogging issues. The PCA results indicated that sedimentological clogging (vertical connectivity cutoff) predominantly occurs in environments dominated by coarse sediment fractions. Specifically, the findings suggest a threshold where clogging impacts considerably decrease when the fraction of fine sediment (< 2 mm) exceeds approximately 50%–55% (Negreiros et al., 2024a). The database also provided insights into the controls and normality of dissolved oxygen in the hyporheic zone of rivers (see Negreiros et al., 2025), with findings indicating a bi-modal statistical distribution, the pivotal role of permeability in controlling the availability of dissolved oxygen, and the characteristics of oxygen profiles among different morphological units. These results provide clear, data-supported insights into sediment-driven riverbed permeability and dissolved oxygen dynamics, contributing valuable information for river restoration strategies targeting vertical connectivity. This practical contribution supports efforts to enhance ecological connectivity and informs sustainable management practices for river systems.

3.6. Ecomorphodynamic landscape optimization

A key aspect of the project was the identification successful restoration design schemes for connectivity. To this end, two restoration sites at the Rhine (i.e., Rastatter Rheinaue and Knoblochsau, see Figure 1) were investigated regarding connectivity patterns and the efficiency of restoration actions. Specifically, at Rastatter Rheinaue, the banks were flattened, and flood protection tracks were selectively lowered to allow for natural erosion and the formation of gravel bars, with the goal of restoring lateral floodplain dynamics. At Kühkopf-Knoblochsau, a 2.5 km stone revetment above the mean water level was removed and bio-engineered willow mattresses were added in areas with high ship-wave attack. Large wood pieces were anchored to steer morphology. The above-listed insights assert the actions at Kühkopf-Knoblochsau particularly high efficiency, suggesting bank removal and large wood placement. The placement of large wood was further investigated by developing a detection algorithm that leverages transfer learning for image classification (Schwindt et al., 2024). Specifically, GoogLeNet was used, which is a robust convolutional neural network pre-trained on a vast array of general images, to classify complex fluvial landscape elements, achieving high recall rates even with constrained datasets. With this algorithm, locations of large wood pieces were identified in large amounts with high accuracy, which is critical for river restoration in general to support biodiversity. The optimized algorithm achieved a remarkable 93.75% recall for large wood identification with as few as 400 labeled instances from the two Rhine sites. This accomplishment contributes to the assessment of restoration efforts, aligning with one of the project's core goal.

Figure 1. Field investigations at the Rhine. (a) Overview of Rhine and the two investigated sites, (b) Rastatter Rheinaue, (c) Knoblochsaue, (d) detailed measurement scheme at a MultiPAC transect (positions 1 – 4) at Knoblochsaue showing the collected frozen sediment samples, (e, f, g), vertical profiles of dissolved oxygen, water temperature and slurping rate measured at the transect.

3.7. Principal outcomes

The hydro-morphological analyses and outcomes of this study contributed in multiple ways to the understanding of river connectivity and its associated spatiotemporal mechanisms. The literature review identified critical gaps in quantification schemes of river connectivity and the de-coupling between hyporheic zone analysis and restoration (Negreiros et al., in review). The project generated key tools to quantify connectivity and guide data-driven river restoration (Negreiros et al., submitted), powered by a robust database and software development techniques, and cutting-edge measurement tools (Negreiros et al., 2023). Thus, restoration measures can now be optimized regarding vertical and lateral connectivity based on the new algorithms and tools for identifying specific hydromorphological phenomena in river systems. In addition, the integration of machine learning with ecological data processing represents one of the main functional achievements of this project, which substantially enhances the efficiency and effectiveness of fluvial landscape classification. For instance, accurate identification of large wood using drone imagery, combined with advanced transfer learning algorithms, enables mapping of ecologically relevant features that support habitat enhancement and flood risk assessment (Schwindt et al., 2024). Finally, with regard to adaptation to climate change, the results (Negreiros et al., submitted) suggest active dynamics in the hyporheic zone of rivers despite drought conditions. Thus, the hyporheic zone of rivers may be an important ally for ensuring resilient ecomorphological systems capable of buffering effects of climate change.

Data availability

In compliance with FAIR principles, the code and data repositories generated in this project were made freely available along with the publications listed in the published project results (section 4). The data associated with the publications currently under review can be accessed at Negreiros et al. (2025a), Negreiros (2025b), and Negreiros and Schwindt (2025c).

References

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- Yang, X., Zhang, S., Li, W., Tang, C., Zhang, J., Schwindt, S., Wieprecht, S., & Wang, T. (2022). Impact of the construction of a dam and spur dikes on the hydraulic habitat of *Megalobrama terminalis* spawning sites: A case study in the Beijiang River (China). *Ecological Indicators*, 143, 109361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2022.109361>

4. Published Project Results (in reverse chronological order)

4.1. Category A – Articles in peer-reviewed journals and contributions to peer-reviewed conferences

- Negreiros B., Wieprecht, S., Schwindt, S. (submitted). Spatial signatures of hyporheic connectivity in a heavily modified waterway. *Hydrology*.
- Negreiros B., Jenkins, C., Schwindt, S., Wieprecht, S. (in review). River connectivity: A comparative review between AI and experts. *Water Resources Research*.
- Negreiros, B., Wieprecht, S., Schwindt, S. (2025d, June 22 – 27). Field measurements point to controls and non-normal dynamics of dissolved oxygen in the hyporheic zone [Conference Article]. In *Proceedings of the 41st IAHR World Congress, International Association for Hydro-Environment Engineering and Research (IAHR), Singapore*.
- Negreiros, B. (2024a, October 15 – 16). Innovative Ansätze und Untersuchungskonzepte zur Quantifizierung von Kolmation in Fließgewässern [Oral Presentation]. *8. Symposium zum technischen Monitoring von Fischen, Themenschwerpunkt Schwall und Sunk sowie Kolmation, Silz, Austria* (Online).
- Negreiros, B., Schwindt, S., Wieprecht, S. (2024b, May 5 – 9). Multi-dimensional river connectivity analyses leveraged by a database approach [Oral Presentation]. *15th International Symposium on Ecohydraulics, Québec city, Québec, Canada*.
- Negreiros, B., Schwindt, S., Scolari, F., Barros, R., Galdos, A.A., Noack, M., Haun, S., Wieprecht, S. (2024c). A database application framework toward data-driven vertical connectivity analysis of rivers. *Environmental Modelling & Software*, 172, 105916. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2023.105916>
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- Schwindt, S., Negreiros, B., Mudiaga-Ojemu, B. O., Hassan, M. A. (2023a). Meta-analysis of a large bedload transport rate dataset. *Geomorphology*, 435, 108748. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geomorph.2023.108748>
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- Negreiros, B., Aybar Galdos, A., Seitz, L., Noack, M., Schwindt, S., Wieprecht, S., Haun, S. (2023). A multi-parameter approach to quantify riverbed clogging and vertical hyporheic connectivity. *River Research and Applications*, 39(8), 1659-1666. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rra.4145>
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- Yang, X., Zhang, S., Li, W., Tang, C., Zhang, J., Schwindt, S., Wieprecht, S., Wang, T. (2022). Impact of the construction of a dam and spur dikes on the hydraulic habitat of *Megalobrama terminalis* spawning sites: A case study in the Beijiang River (China). *Ecological Indicators* 143, 109361. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolind.2022.109361>

4.2. Category B – Any other form of published results

- Marx, F. (2025) *From picture to depth-explicit grain size characteristics* [Bachelor's Thesis]. Eigenverlag des Instituts für Wasser- und Umweltsystemmodellierung.
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